

SOFRINNOV

Ecological construction recycled and recyclable

A combination of used wood pallets and Lego-like connectors called SYCLAT® allows for very simple and setup of shelter and leisure houses. The houses are completely reversible and recyclable and can be used as short-time and low budget accommodation or be equipped with more durable wall insulation and roofing.

Highlights of innovative features

- The walls of the construction are made from used pallets that are joined with SYCLAT® Lego-like connectors. Each pallet increasing the wall size by 1m² within seconds, allows for very fast construction.
- The system being very simple, no significant training nor machines other than a cordless screwdriver are needed.
- The constructions are suitable for leisure and temporary accommodation or offices in a price range of €500 to €850 per m².
- If used inside existing buildings (e.g. production halls, trade fairs, office spaces) the price range drops to €150 to €350 per m².

Simple but highly effective constructive measures prevent the wood from getting wet through water stagnation or capillary effects (e.g. used tire chunks as separators). In this way, the wood remains sufficiently dry to exclude attacks of wood decaying fungi.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #14 | 2021

SOFRINNOV
40 Chemin de Lasbadorques
31700 Cornebarrieu
FRANCE

